

MAJOR PAPER**LAST NAME: Maekawa****FIRST NAME: Shu****PROGRAM CODE: DCTD****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 1****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma****Edit or delete text to show the actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use **Turabian/Chicago footnote references** (with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did **not** use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did **not** use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: No plagiarism detected

The author used the following software (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

List your 5-7 critical concepts with the page number in the text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. US style (EUCLID 2024, 25-32)
2. ...

HOW TO SELECT THE MOST PROPER SETS OF RULES IN WRITING AN ACADEMIC PAPER ON MANY CONDITIONS

1) INTRODUCTION

In the first course, I studied the basics of writing rules for academic papers. To be honest, until now, I have not had enough experience to write an academic paper in English, and I can do it if it is not formally academic occasions. Therefore, deciding which academic style is appropriate for me and each situation is not an easy matter because there are few determiners I should consider. However, sometimes I have to choose from several rules because there are some options to select for styles and **sets of rules** that are presented in the course materials, such as **US-style and UK-style**. In this response paper, I state the process that I have to go through in order to be consistent in one specific academic paper.

In other words, I must understand the background to determine which of some specific styles is better than the others because each style has its own advantages and disadvantages in several writing situations. Therefore, in this paper, as the starting point, I compare the US-style and UK-style characteristics and the reason why I will choose one of each, at least in specific situations.

2) US STYLE VS UK STYLE

According to the EUCLID material, there is **US-style writing and UK-style writing**. Before judging either of them is better than the other, I confirm the basics of our decision for writing and citation style. Generally, students who have experienced the US educational system are familiar with the US style, and those who have experienced the UK educational system are familiar with the **UK style**. In Japan, I experienced the UK style as the main road in the traditional history department in the humanity department of the University of Tokyo.

Understanding these basics and experiences, I even state that there are several rational factors that encourage us to select one of them. Firstly, the UK style is compact in terms of citation, meaning that intext citation requires less writing effort. By contrast, the US style asks the writer to make citations as long footnotes. This comparative fact gives us insights that if most of the readers are not familiar with the academic field or backgrounds of the dissertation, It might be better to choose the US style because the readers can acquire knowledge about relevant academic materials directly in the footnotes. On the contrary, if the readers of the dissertation are familiar with the academic fields of the paper and the author him/herself, the UK style is better because there is a higher probability that readers can understand whom and where the intext citations originally existed and what they specifically mean in the original texture.

However, I state that there are several rational components that let us determine each of the options according to the writing purpose and personal situation. For example, as for intext reference, the **UK style** is allowed to use its main method, but the US style allows the author to make **footnotes** in detail afterward (EUCLID 2024, 25-32). This means that when the thesis that we are writing has shared background knowledge about relevant documents, the **UK style** is more effective. By contrast, the US style is better when there is detailed and direct information in the **footnotes**. For example, the traditional history thesis requires or contains a large amount of references to the raw documents. In this case, the author should inform the readers of what sources he/she cited and used as a basis for the statement.

3) MY FEELINGS TOWARD THE US AND UK STYLE

I am rather attracted by the **UK style** because I experienced UK academic life when I was a bachelor's student, and intext reference is very simple and visibly easy for many beginners. Moreover, when I wrote my bachelor thesis, it was tough to list all of the references in the **footnotes**, which was accelerated by the academic discipline I committed, that is, "traditional occidental history." Too many references that I had completed with deep effort were correctly and positively evaluated by the department of my university, but I thought I would have been focused more on the content or reasoning of the thesis in itself. Both could have been done if I had been Superman, but time was limited in reality. However, as a graduate student, I have now adopted the UK style for the rational reasons that I explained above.

4) CONCLUSION

As I mentioned above, there are some rational reasons why the author chose a specific writing style. What I want to say especially is that I agree that **consistency in itself** is the most important in terms of persuasion and authority of academic papers; some deficiencies may occur even if the author chooses a traditionally correct style. For me, it is just an unavoidable error. In conclusion, we should be confident in our style choices and be tolerant of other decision-makers if there is rational consistency in the style used in the academic paper. I suggest my conclusion can be applied to other rules like Turiban, WHO, etc. “Be rational, consistent, and tolerant.”

5) MY OWN IMPRESSION

Throughout my academic career, I have not placed much emphasis on the consistency of my writing style. This course introduction is truly helpful and practical forever, even if the traditional style might be going to be slightly changed. For now, I have decided to adopt the UK style, but day by day, I will study another set of rules. One of my academic goals is to conduct research on counterterrorism policy in the Nigerian polity. Still, regardless of this goal, I think these kinds of basic educational benefits are necessary, so I will review this RP many times. I will remember the importance of the **consistency** and adopting the most appropriate sets of writing rules. Thank you very much for your correction about the RP rule and my faults. To be honest, I want to study counterterrorism in Western Africa early, and this course is mentally tough for me, but I promise to apply this experience in the first course to the final dissertation and, more broadly, continuing study in EUCLID.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA401D Cousepack: Period 1*. Fifth edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.